

LEVERAGING BIG DATA FOR MANAGING TRANSPORT OPERATIONS

Deliverable 6.1

LeMO Project Fact Sheet

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Work Package 6

Project Coordinator

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MG-8-2-2017 - Big data in Transport: Research opportunities, challenges and limitations

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Disclaimer:

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Idea

Big data has opened a wide spectrum of opportunities in the field of transport research. Observing the recent growing interest in the application of big data within transport, as well as the extended scope of its applications, it is evident that most of the challenges have yet to be addressed.

Figure 1 Five transport dimensions

The project called **Leveraging Big Data to Manage Transport Operations (LeMO)** will explore the implications of the utilisation of big data to enhance the economic sustainability and competitiveness of European transport sector. The project will study and analyse big data in the European transport domain addressing five transport dimensions: mode, sector, technology, policy and evaluation.

LeMO will accomplish this by conducting a series of case studies, in

order to provide recommendations on the prerequisites of effective big data implementation in the transport field.

Case Studies

LeMO will conduct primary and secondary research on a series of seven case studies in the following areas:

Figure 2 LeMO case studies

These case studies will produce evidence-based, clear and precise questions based on rigorous knowledge that illuminate opportunities, problems and possible solutions to be further investigated in the LeMO roadmap. The identification of these issues will be complemented by a horizontal analysis to identify challenges, opportunities, limitations and other consequences of cross-disciplinary nature, and thus relevant to transport big data as a whole.

LeMO will use these case studies and its reference & advisory board to create a roadmap and provide recommendations for better use of big data in European Transport. The LeMO roadmap will be divided into:

- Essential policy steps, and
- Essential research steps

for transport industry to reach a greater share of the big data market and to improve the competitiveness of European transport industry.

Expected key results

- Understanding and mapping big data in European transport
- Research roadmap for the efficient utilisation of big data in transport
- Policy roadmap for the efficient utilisation of big data in transport
- Creating Shared Value for the European transport

The final result of LeMO will lead to an imperative, more effective big data economy in Europe that addresses the needs and concerns of science, industry, policy-makers and citizens as well as stakeholders and drive the European transport industry forward.

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